

HIGH TEMPERATURE CHARACTERISATION AND STRUCTURAL
ANALYSIS OF PRD-166 ALUMINA ZIRCONIA FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

The PRD-166 fibre is fabricated by E.I. Du Pont de Nemours. It is continuous, having a diameter of about 18 μm , and is composed of 80% alpha alumina and 20% zirconia. The PRD-166 fibre is of interest as a possible reinforcement for thermostructural composite materials. The microstructure of the fibre has been studied in parallel with its mechanical characterisation from room temperature to 1300°C. Three grain sizes have been observed with the largest alumina grains, being around 1 μm in size and surrounded by much smaller microcrystallites, the former acting as defects which limit the strength of the fibre at temperatures at which the tensile behaviour is linearly elastic. At higher temperatures the tensile behaviour of the fibre becomes non-linear and the microstructural mechanisms more complex.

KEYWORDS : Fibre, ceramic ; elevated temperature ; failure mechanism ; microstructure ; electron microscopy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Small diameter ceramic fibres are at present attracting increasing interest as reinforcements for metals, glasses and ceramics. The oxide fibres are particularly interesting as they cannot be deteriorated by oxidation at high temperature as is the case with many other fibres.

The PRD-166 fibre is the second generation of alumina based fibres produced by E.I. Du Pont de Nemours and according to its manufacturer shows enhanced strength when compared to its almost pure α -alumina predecessor Fibre FP (1). The PRD-166 fibre is composed of 80% α -alumina and 20% zirconia partially stabilised with yttrium oxide. The fibre is made by drawing a filament consisting of the ceramics in powder form together with an organo metallic binder which then undergoes two thermal treatments to produce the densified ceramic fibre (2).

The manufacturer has announced that the fibre conserves its mechanical properties to very high temperatures. For example 75% room temperature strength retention after two hours at 1400°C.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEEDURE

2.1. Microstructural Characterisation The general appearance of the fibre has been observed with a Philips EM 501 scanning electron microscope. Fracture surfaces have been observed with a scanning electron microscope equipped with a field effect gun (JEOL 6400 F) in order to increase the resolution. The identification of the different phases has been made by X-ray diffraction using a Siemens D500 diffractometer equipped with a $\text{CoK}\alpha_1$, $\text{K}\alpha_2$ (40 kV, 20 mA, iron filter) source and an Elphyse detector equipped with a linear proportional counter. The crystallinity, the identification of different phases and the grain size distribution have been studied using a Philips EM 430 (300 kV and 2.4 Å resolution) transmission electron microscope coupled with an energy dispersive X-ray analyser (TRACOR). Specimens were prepared using two techniques. The fibres were embedded in epoxy resin and then mechanically polished to obtain a disc about 50 µm thick. Final thinning to a thickness of less than 100 nm was made by ion etching. The second technique was to thin the fibres directly by ion etching. In this case the fibres were held between two nickel rings.

2.2. Mechanical Characterisation Tensile tests have been conducted on single fibres using a cross-head speed of 0.75 mm/mn over the temperature range from 23°C to 1300°C. The fibre was positioned in the grips and then the furnace was slid over it. The fibre was held at temperature for three minutes before starting the test.

3. MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION

3.1. General appearance The PRD-166 fibres are supplied in the form of continuous rovings. The individual fibres are circular in cross section with a diameter, as determined, statistically by image analysis of scanning electron micrographs, of 17.6 ± 0.3 µm. Their surface is rough, typical of a multi crystalline material and grains visible at the surface were of the order of 0.5 µm, as can be seen in Figure 1. The fibres possess a high elastic modulus and this, coupled with a low strain to failure, made handling them rather difficult.

3.2. Microstructure The as received PRD-166 fibres were found to be completely crystalline with no amorphous phase being detected by X-ray diffraction nor electron diffraction in TEM. The fibre is composed of two crystalline phases, 80% α-alumina and 20% tetragonal zirconia, both distributed uniformly in the volume of the fibre. The microstructure is complex with several grains superposed in the specimens examined, which were less than 100 nm thick, and a large dispersion in the grain sizes, as shown in Figure 2.

Three sizes of crystal were observed :

from 0.1 to 1 μm prismatic grains of α -alumina

from 0.1 to 0.5 μm prismatic grains of zirconia

about 20 nm microcrystallites of alumina and zirconia surrounding the larger grains.

This granulometry appears to have its origin in the size dispersions of the ceramic powder used during fibre manufacture and preferential grain growth of the larger alumina crystals, at the expense of the small grains, during the final heat treatment of the densification phase.

The presence of very thin films at some grain boundaries has been observed having thicknesses of around 1 nm between alumina grains and 0.5 nm between zirconia grains (3). As these dimensions are of the order of atomic spacings in the crystal phases it seems unrealistic to speculate on the existence of an amorphous phase.

Twinning of tetragonal zirconia crystals has been observed which could arise during rapid cooling of cubic zirconia doped with yttrium oxide (4).

The crystalline structure of the fibre showed a tendency to be orientated such that the c-axis of the hexagonal alumina was perpendicular to the fibre axis. This has been shown by a comparative study of X-ray diffraction patterns by transmission and in reflection from (110) and (166) planes of the alumina. This orientation is probably due to grain growth during the final stage of fibre production.

3.3. Microstructural evolution with Temperature Exposure for four hours at 850°C produced a marked change in the microstructure which was considerably simplified, as shown in Figure 3. Growth of alumina grains has been observed. The majority of grains were around 0.5 μm but some microcrystallites still existed. The larger grains were seen not to have developed. The microcrystallites of zirconia had also grown but to a less extent to around 100 nm. This was confirmed by there being few observable Moiré fringes due to the superpositioning of grains. Dislocations were observed around small grains, of about 100 nm, in contact with larger grains of about 1 μm indicating induced stresses due to thermal expansion.

Heat treatment for four hours at 1200°C produced a similar microstructure to that produced at 850°C with a slight increase in the size of the grains.

4. MECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION

4.1. At Room Temperature The PRD-166 were found to be linearly elastic at room temperature with a failure morphology typical of brittle failure. Figure 4.

A series of forty tensile tests were conducted at various gauge lengths. The results of these tests are shown in Table 1. (The values in bracket show the standard deviations of the results).

Gauge length (mm)	Failure stress (MPa)	Strain (%)	Young Modulus (GPa)
9	1549 (372)		
45	1561 (370)		
220	1480 (369)	0.41 (0.09)	373 (50)

Table 1 : Results of tensile tests, at various gauge length, of PRD-166 fibres tested at 23°C.

For comparison the characteristics of the FP fibres as announced by the manufacture are shown in Table 2.

64	1380 (200)	0.4 (0.09)	380 (55)
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Table 2 : Published values for the FP fibres (5).

A comparison of Tables 1 and 2 reveals a slight improvement of the properties of the PRD-166 fibres

Two types of failure morphology were observed at room temperature, inter and transgranular. Figure 5. The intergranular failure produced crystal pullout and involved grains of all sizes as well as crystal clusters where as cleavage was rarely observed in the largest alumina grains. The irregular nature of the fracture surface meant that it was difficult to determine the origin of the failures. Figure 6.

4.2. Characterisation at high temperature The tensile tests on single PRD 166-fibre at high temperature were conducted using a gauge length of 150 mm. Table 3 summarises the results obtained.

Temperature (°C)	Failure stress (MPa)	Strain (%)	Young Modulus (GPa)
20	1470 (280)	0.41 (0.08)	363 (42)
830	1270 (250)	0.41 (0.06)	313 (48)
980	1270 (210)	0.39 (0.04)	322 (48)
1180	830 (210)	0.30 (0.05)	275 (37)
1250	540 (120)		

Table 3 : Results of tensile tests on PRD-166 at various temperature.

The PRD-166 fibres was observed to retain 86% of its initial strength up to 1000°C however a 63% loss in strength was seen at 1250°C. The loss in

strength was found to begin between 1100°C and 1180°C.

The behaviour of the PRD-166 fibre was observed to be linearly elastic up to 1180°C. However above this temperature behaviour was non longer linear as shown by Figure 7. The gradient of the tensile curve varied during the test and the failure load was no longer equal to the maximum load supported by the fibre during the test. At 1300°C the fibre was found to creep extensively during the test.

Superplasticity has been observed with certain fibres from as low a temperature as 830°C. The fibres were found to deform linearly elastically until yielding occurred which was then followed by elongation and at a reduced load level, as shown in Figure 8. Observation of the microstructure of fibre which exhibited such behaviour revealed few dislocations but evidence of considerable grain growth in the direction of the fibre axis as shown in Figure 9.

Failure morphology of fibres tested at 1250°C revealed the two types of fracture seen at room temperature but with fewer failures by cleavage. Figure 10.

5. DISCUSSIONS

Unlike most ceramics and fibres the PRD-166 fibres were found not to obey an inverse relationship between strength and specimen volume. The average failure strength of the fibre was found to be independant of gauge length. It is probable that the large alumina grains observed to be uniformly distributed along the fibre account for the absence of an effect of gauge length and control ultimate failure at room temperature. This means that there is a high probability of finding a large grain in the shortest gauge length tested. These large grains are embedded in a matrix of much smaller grains with a random arrangement. As the α form of alumina is a highly anisotropic crystalline structure ($a = 0,478 \text{ nm}$ $c = 1,299 \text{ nm}$) and the associated expansion coefficients are equally anisotropic considerable internal stresses can be expected to occur in the vicinity of large grains during sintering (6). These stresses can be expected to increase as the temperature is decreased. This, coupled with stress concentrations induced by the geometrical effects of having a large grain embedded in the fibre would facilitate failure in the neighbourhood of such grains and encourage grain pull out.

Failure is usually by crack propagation following the weaker grain boundaries. Occasional grain cleavage has been observed. However this requires much greater energy. Cleavage occurs most probably when the grain is orientated in such a way as to present its weakest crystallographic plane to the crack tip which is constrained by the relative orientations of other grains resulting in strong boundaries.

Plane	Fracture surface energy (J/m ²) at room temperature
(1 0 $\bar{1}$ 1)	6.0
(1 0 $\bar{1}$ 0)	7.3
(1 1 $\bar{2}$ 3)	24.0
(0 0 0 1)	> 40.0

Table 4 : Failure energy at room temperature of α -alumina as a function of crystallographic orientation (7).

At high temperatures the behaviour of the fibre changes as creep is observed. The structure of the fibre evolves and involves grain growth. The applied stress increases the probability of diffusion and hence grain growth. Creep is therefore controlled by diffusion in the direction of stress and given the small grain sizes, less than one micron, it is probable that the Coble mechanism predominates (8): Ions diffuse across the grain boundaries which are preferential routes for diffusion rather than diffusion inside grains across the crystalline network. However as few dislocations were seen it is probable that creep by the sliding of dislocations is a secondary mechanism.

The role of the zirconia in the fibre is not clear but does not appear to be simply based on a change of crystallographic form.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The PRD-166 fibre has been seen to possess improved mechanical properties when compared to the earlier, all α -alumina FP fibre. The α -alumina and zirconia in the PRD-166 fibre give the structure three distinct grains size populations. The largest grains, up to 1 μm are of α -alumina whilst the zirconia can also be seen to exist in the form of grains of 0.1 to 0.5 μm . These relatively large crystals are surrounded by much smaller crystals of the same materials with sizes of the order of 10 nm. Grain growth occurs at temperatures as low as 850°C and in some cases superplasticity has been observed.

Failure both at room temperature and at higher temperatures can involve grains pull out and cleavage with the former being predominant. The large grains of α -alumina are most probably the source of stress concentrations due both to the geometrical effects but also due to the build up of residual stresses caused by differences in thermal expansions amongst the irregularly orientated grains.

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Figure 1 : S.E.M. image
General aspect of the PRD166 fibre.

Figure 2 : T.E.M. image
Complex microstructure of the fibre at room temperature.

Figure 3 : T.E.M. image
Simplification of the microstructure after heat treatment at 850°C for 4 hours.

Figure 4 : Strength strain curve at room temperature
typical of brittle behaviour.

Figure 5 : S.E.M. image
Fracture surface of the fibre after tensile test at room temperature (inter and transgranular failure).

Figure 6 : S.E.M. image
Irregular nature of the fracture surface of the fibre after tensile test at room temperature.

Figure 7 : Strength strain curves at high temperature.

Figure 8 : Strength strain curve at 830°C showing superplasticity.

0.5 μm

Figure 9 : T.E.M. image

General aspect of the fibre after tensile test at 1100°C showing oriented grain growth.

Figure 10 : S.E.M. with a field effect gun image

Fracture surface of the fibre after tensile test at 1250°C.